

Original Research

Prediction of the Impact of Bank Failure Risk on Micro-Credit in Iran: An Artificial Intelligence Approach

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to predict the impact of bank default risk on microcredit in Iran. Given the importance of microcredit in creating employment and reducing poverty and inequality, it is necessary to investigate the factors affecting access to these loans due to increased bank default risk. This study was conducted with a quantitative research approach and the data of all 28 Iranian banks in the period from 2017 to 2022 were analyzed. Machine learning tools, including artificial neural networks (ANN) and support vector machine (SVM), were used to analyze macroeconomic indicators such as GDP, inflation, exchange rate, interest rate, and financial variables of banks such as investment volume, amount of loans granted, total deposits, and bankruptcy risk indicators. The results showed that the increase in bankruptcy risk of banks has an inverse and significant relationship with the number of microloans. The developed models predicted this relationship with high accuracy and reliability, such that the accuracy of the ANN model was 100% and that of the SVM model was 95%. Thus, this study shows that the factors related to macroeconomic conditions and financial condition of banks serve as warning signals for the reduction of microcredit. On this basis, policy makers are recommended to focus on the financial stability of banks, increasing their resilience to economic shocks and reforming macroeconomic structures to avoid restricting access to microcredit and its negative impact on the economy.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Bankruptcy risk, Machine learning, Microcredits.

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Introduction

Financing is vital for the economic growth of any country. This process involves the collection of financial resources and directing them towards priority investments, which facilitates economic growth (Habibolahpour Zarashki, et al., 2023). Banks play a key role in this economic ecosystem, as they provide a strong foundation for financing and investment through the collection of deposits, which in turn helps in the advancement and development of the economy (Hafezi, 2014). The mission of banks includes meeting the financial needs of businesses, ranging from seasonal funding to purchasing raw materials and expanding production lines (Weber, 2011). These financial actions help in the long-term growth of companies, making banks a vital source of financing. In addition to this, by participating in various economic projects, banks increase their income, which strengthens their profitability (Giebel, et al., 2020).

However, like other economic institutions, banks are continuously faced with risks such as bankruptcy. These risks can arise from the imbalance between bank assets and liabilities, especially during crisis situations (Climent, et al., 2019). Banks usually have liabilities that need to be paid immediately upon depositors' requests, while the granted loans are recorded as long-term assets. In normal conditions, the mismatch between the maturity of liabilities and receivables usually does not pose a problem, since withdrawals do not occur simultaneously and loans are repaid at specified maturities (Izadiniya, et al., 2017). A banking institution mitigates the risk of loss from delinquent receivables with its initial capital, and liquid assets ensure that the bank can cover its immediate liabilities (Ansori, et al., 2019). However, situations like unanticipated increases in withdrawals can disrupt this delicate balance, exposing the bank to liquidity risks and eventually bankruptcy. Such crises can have widespread economic consequences, including a decrease in public trust in banks and can cause the bankruptcy of other banks (Raz, 2022).

One of the consequences that arise from bank bankruptcies is the disruption in the granting of loans and microcredits. Obtaining loans and credit from financial institutions plays a crucial role in financing various economic activities. Credit and loans directly and indirectly affect the employment of production units and the creation of new job opportunities (Lohmann, et al., 2023). In the short term, providing small loans and credits to manufacturing enterprises as working capital can lead to increased employment. This impact occurs in terms of the stability of the capital volume (Alabi, et al., 2022). Conversely, over longer periods, where financial flows transform into fixed capital, changes resulting from technological advancements become apparent. (Tayebi, et al., 2010) Nevertheless, research has shown that when banks encounter problems and even face bankruptcy, it can have a very negative impact on the economy. When banks experience difficulties, they are often unable to provide the necessary loans for purchases or investments, which can be particularly challenging and sometimes impossible for small businesses that need bank financing. This lack of financing can hinder growth and even lead to the closure of small businesses. Following this restriction in lending, businesses unable to secure the funding necessary to continue operations may be forced to reduce or cease their activities, impacting their employees and customers. The reduction in business activities and job losses can result in fewer individuals being able to save or spend money, leading to decreased demand for goods and services. All these factors lead to an overall

reduction in economic activities and exacerbate economic inequalities in society, as low-income individuals and families are typically more affected by unemployment and reduced income (Contreras, et al., 2023). On the other hand, limited research has been conducted on the impact of bank bankruptcies on income distribution through changes in the allocation of loans for small businesses (Ou, et al., 2009). Moreover, there are limited studies on the impact of banking bankruptcy on microcredits in Iran. Therefore, this research aims to examine and analyze the impact of banking bankruptcy risk on microcredits in Iran using genetic algorithms in neural networks, which could be beneficial for policymakers and managers in the banking sector and financial systems. Consequently, the main objective of this study is to predict the effects of banking bankruptcy risk on microcredits in Iran using genetic algorithms in neural networks. Initially, this research will assess the relationships between the study's variables and their importance in predicting the risk of bankruptcy on microcredits using decision tree algorithms and gradient boosting. Following that, the research model will be evaluated and assessed using ANN (Artificial Neural Networks) and SVM (Support Vector Machines) learning networks.

Research Literature

In the past, banks played a central role in financing and economic development. In his book "The Wealth of Nations" (1776), Adam Smith emphasized the importance of banks in facilitating trade and economic growth. He argued that banks increase liquidity and encourage investment by taking deposits and making loans (Smith, 1776). Furthermore, in "The Theory of Economic Development", Schumpeter (1911) emphasized the crucial role of credit in promoting innovation and economic growth. He explained that access to credit enables entrepreneurs to realize new ideas and create new industries (Schumpeter, 1991).

Banks play a central role in the monetary structure of every country and are crucial for capital provision, money, and wealth transfer (Hassan, et al., 2023). With support and credit from the central bank, they collect deposits and thus play a fundamental role in the economic flow and liquidity creation through various financial services and facilities. However, banks may face crises due to various reasons linked to internal operations or domestic and international economic conditions (Farhang, et al., 2016). In such crisis situations, not only do macroeconomic variables get affected, but there are also consequences for micro-segments and individuals in society. In the event of bank bankruptcies, access to microcredits is limited, subsequently reducing opportunities for employment and income generation, which can directly negatively impact poverty reduction and inequality (Neifar, et al., 2023).

Microcredits are small loans designed to help low-income individuals and small businesses achieve financial independence by starting or expanding economic activities, thus contributing to poverty reduction (Khoshbakht, et al., 2022). This type of credit is usually provided by banks and has conditions that facilitate access to financial resources for people with limited credit history or for those who cannot provide traditional collateral (Hassan et al, 2023). Microcredit can play an essential role in people's economic empowerment and social development (Moshiri, et al., 2012). Therefore, microcredit plays a key role in the financial cycle of countries as an effective tool to economically

empower families and reduce poverty and inequality (Ratnawati, 2020). These loans, which usually come with repayment modalities better suited to the needs of low-income groups, enable people in the community who normally do not have access to banking services to access financial resources (Divandari, 2016).

Bankruptcy risk refers to the probability of a financial institution's inability to settle its debts. This situation can arise from various factors, including mismanagement of assets, sudden market changes, or failures in risk assessment and management, and can significantly affect the health of the financial and banking system (Horváthová, et al., 2018). If a bank is at risk of bankruptcy, it can undermine public trust in the entire banking system, resulting in widespread withdrawals and eventual financial collapse (Kaufman, 2004). The spread of bankruptcies can quickly trouble the entire financial system; therefore, specific regulations and careful oversight of the financial system must be employed to prevent such conditions (Taghdir, 2013). Therefore, there are certain studies at the global level that are reviewed below

Ebrahimi Salari et al (2013). explored the role of money endowments in Islamic microfinance and concluded that money endowment has the potential to be used as a source of Islamic finance, particularly in microfinance, through simulations of money endowment behavior in Islamic countries.

Zarei and Komijani (2015). conducted a study on the identification and investigation of banking crises in Iran, determining that variables like real currency growth and real GDP growth can predict banking crises through an analysis of economic indicators.

Ahmadian (2015). developed a bankruptcy forecasting system based on ownership and identified key variables affecting Iranian banks' survival through data analysis of 13 predictive variables, suggesting the need for regulatory monitoring. Grasa, 2016, examined ownership structure and bankruptcy risk in GCC Islamic banks and found that the income structure affects bankruptcy risk, with Islamic banks having a higher risk linked to profit-sharing products, using a three-stage least squares method.

Sarmiento et al (2016). analyzed the impact of risk-taking on cost and profit efficiency in Colombian banks, discovering that risk-taking can reduce inefficiencies while credit and market risks could improve profit efficiency through advanced modeling techniques.

Hartmann et al (2017). studied the impact of economic complexity on income inequality and determined that higher economic complexity correlates with better income distribution, limiting income inequality, through the analysis of data from 150 countries.

Kabir Hassan et al (2018). assessed liquidity risk management in Islamic versus non-Islamic banks and concluded that Islamic banks manage risks better than non-Islamic banks, with machine learning improving risk prediction accuracy.

Adam et al (2019). examined the economic complexity effect on labor markets and found that higher economic complexity is associated with higher employment and lower unemployment rates through data analysis.

Chu and Hoang (2020). investigated the impact of economic complexity on income inequality, linking higher economic complexity to greater income inequality via international data analysis.

Contreras et al (2023). explored the impact of bank bankruptcies on small business loans and income inequality using a difference-in-differences method, concluding that bank bankruptcies increase income inequality by reducing access to small business loans, which subsequently decreases income.

Mahaputri et al (2024). examined lending to SMEs and unemployment rates in Indonesia, revealing that lending to SMEs significantly reduces unemployment while bank branches and inflation positively affect SME lending through random effects and fixed effects models.

According to the review of theoretical literature and background, the experimental results show that there are no studies on the positive effects of microcredit and no serious study on the effect of banks on credit. On the other hand, the studies that directly examine the risk prediction of banks on microcredits in Iran have not been observed, which has a research gap in this regard. In addition, the present study uses neural networks which have not been used in previous studies in this area. The results are expected to contribute to the expansion of theoretical and empirical literature in this area and to fill the research gaps.

Methodology

In today's dynamic financial world, banks, as the main financial institutions, play a vital role in economic development. The financial stability and health of banks is of utmost importance to ensure the proper functioning of the country's financial system and economy. Bank bankruptcy, as one of the systemic risks, can have adverse and severe economic consequences, including disruption of access to microcredit, which has significant consequences on economic growth and financial sustainability. In Iran's economy, historical experiences and current conditions have turned the issue of bank bankruptcy into a topic of interest and study (Safarzadeh, et al., 2019). Predicting the effects of bank bankruptcy on microcredit is an issue that requires the use of advanced and accurate analytical methods in order to be able to optimally manage risk with a deeper understanding of the complexities and effective factors. In this regard, the use of non-parametric quantitative methods that do not require traditional assumptions of data distribution can be very useful (Ahmadyan, et al., 2017). Decision trees, reinforcement rounds, support vector machines (SVMs), and artificial neural networks (ANNs) are among the methods that have the ability to detect complex patterns in data and provide high-precision predictions. These methods can help to uncover latent structural relationships and identify important indicators that may play an important role in the occurrence of bank bankruptcy (Sarkani, et al., 2018); (Mokhtari, et al., 2014). This study aims to predict the impact of bankruptcy risk of Iranian banks on microcredit using the financial and economic data of Iranian banks, which will be used using decision tree, reinforcement rounds, support vector machines (SVMs) and artificial neural networks (ANNs). In the following, we will carefully examine each of these methods and how they are applied in the subject in question.

The methodology of this research is based on quantitative approach and descriptive-analytical research design. The statistical population of this research includes all active banks in the banking system of Iran in the period of 2017 to 2022. Based on the total number of banks, including 28 banks according to Table (1), they were selected as a sample. Audited financial statements of banks, central bank reports and Tehran Stock Exchange database were used to collect the required data. To analyses the data and predict the impact of bank bankruptcy risk on microcredit, machine learning techniques including decision tree, gradient boosting, support vector machine (SVM) and artificial neural network (ANN) are used. First, the data is pre-processed and prepared for building predictive models. The information gain (IG) criterion is used to select optimal features in the decision tree (Nazemi Ardakani, et al., 2018). The built models will be evaluated using the criteria of accuracy, correctness, recall and error rate. Finally, the best model is selected for prediction. Also, to investigate the impact of other macroeconomic variables on microcredit, the model of Contreras et al (2023) will be used, which considers variables such as inflation rate, exchange rate and interest rate. To measure the risk of bank failure, the composite index proposed by Contreras et al (2023) is used, which takes into account the value of the bank, liquidity, assets, facilities received from the central bank and facilities granted by the bank.

Table 1. Names Banks

Bank type	row	Name of the bank	Number of branches
State commercial banks	1	Sepah	1757
	2	Post Bank	406
	3	national	3692
State specialized banks	1	Export development	33
	2	Industry and mining	64
	3	agriculture	1914
	4	housing	1233
	5	Cooperative development	458
	1	New economy	265
	2	the Persians	293
	3	entrepreneur	100
	4	Saman	150
	5	Pasargad	328
	6	capital	154
	7	Sinai	263
	8	city	258
	9	Dey	370
	10	business	1800
	11	Welfare of workers	1083
	12	Export	33000
Non-government banks	13	nation	1815
	14	Iranian wisdom	125
	15	tourism	50
	16	Iran is the land	351
	18	Middle East	11

Bank type	row	Name of the bank	Number of branches
	17	the future	165
	18	Iran and Venezuela	1
Qarz-ul-Hasna banks	1	Mehr - Economy	735
	2	Resalat	306

In this study, decision tree and gradient boosting tree algorithms were used to predict the impact of bank bankruptcy risk on microcredit in Iran. The decision tree method creates a tree-like structure to illustrate the decision-making process. Relevant data were collected, pre-processed, and used to build and train the decision tree model. The information gain criterion was used to select optimal features for splitting data and creating tree nodes (Zhang, et al., 2011). In addition, the gradient boosting tree algorithm, a state-of-the-art machine learning technique, was employed. This method aims to reduce the errors of previous models by sequentially adding new models. Results from this approach have demonstrated improved accuracy compared to conventional techniques such as linear regression and simple classification methods (Siasar, et al., 2020).

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are computational models inspired by the structure and function of the human brain. These networks are composed of interconnected layers, with each layer containing artificial neurons. Each neuron receives weighted inputs and calculates the output using an activation function (Ghadimi, et al., 2002). The basic formula for the output of a neuron is $y = f(\sum (w_i * x_i) + b)$. During the training process, the network adjusts the weights and biases using the error backpropagation algorithm to minimize the error between the predicted output and the actual value. Neural networks are capable of learning complex patterns in data and are utilized in a wide range of applications such as image recognition, natural language processing, and time series prediction.

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a robust supervised learning technique primarily used for classification. SVM is a non-parametric model that, despite requiring more computational power than its parametric counterparts, has forcefully entered the world of predictive models due to the development of new advanced technologies and the continuously growing size of datasets (Rastegar, 2017). In this research, artificial neural networks have been used to predict the effects of bankruptcy risk on microcredit. Therefore, to evaluate the classification methods employed for detecting the impact of Iranian banks' bankruptcy risk on microcredit, the criteria for assessing algorithm accuracy, obtained error, and prediction accuracy are examined. Accuracy, precision, recall, and classification error rate are used to evaluate the performance of the proposed models. Accuracy represents the ratio of correctly classified samples to total samples. Precision indicates the ratio of correctly classified positive samples to total predicted positive samples. Recall shows the ratio of correctly classified positive samples to total actual positive samples. The classification error rate is calculated by subtracting accuracy from 100 percent (Sokolova, et al., 2009v).

Finally, by comparing the results obtained from various machine learning models including decision tree, gradient boosting, artificial neural network, and support vector machine, the best model for predicting the impact of bank bankruptcy risk on microcredit in Iran will be selected. This study can assist policymakers and decision-makers in the

banking system to optimally manage risk by gaining a deeper understanding of the influencing factors and complexities of this issue (Karimi, et al., 2019).

Model Clarification

In this study based on the variables of the Contreras et al (2023) model. The impact of bank bankruptcy on the granting of credit to the micro unit is studied, so in order to estimate the research relationship, first, the variables of inflation, exchange rate, and interest rate are considered as a function of the variables of the rituals reflecting the macroeconomic situation of Contreras et al (2023). It is considered that in this case, it will be as follows:

$$\text{CAMELS} = \text{inflation} + \text{exchange rate} + \text{interest rate}$$

In this function, based on the study of Contreras et al (2023). CAMELS represents the economic situation variable, which consists of inflation data as the inflation variable (consumer price index), exchange rate which represents the exchange rate, and interest rate in the research model represents the real interest rate (inflation minus the official interest rate)The data related to this part of the research have been extracted from the Central Bank of the Islamic Republic of Iran, the Coins and Currency website, and the Economic and Financial Data Bank, which will be as follows:

$$\text{Tlgsu} = f(\text{Camels} + \text{bankruptcy} + \text{gdp} + \text{investment} + \text{Tdiwb})$$

In this function, TLGSU represents the granting of credits per microunit, (GDP) represents GDP (nominal fixed per capita excluding oil and gas), (Investment) represents the investments made by the bank (credits allocated by the bank to production units and investors), and (TDIWB) represents the total deposits of the right people in the bank. As a variable, it indicates the bankruptcy risk, which (bankruptcy) is measured according to Contreras et al. (2023) as (bank bankruptcy risk = bank value + total liquidity in the bank's hands + total current and non-current assets + total credits received by the bank from the central bank of the locality + total loans granted by the bank).

Finally, it should be said that the present study will be conducted for Iranian banks listed in the Tehran Stock Exchange for the period from 2017 to 2022. In general, the research variables and their symbol are in the form of Table 2.

Table 2. Definition of Research Variables

Variable Title	Symbol	Data Source	Unit of measure
Granting credits to micro-units	TLGSU	cbi.ir/page/4275.aspx	Billion Rials
Macroeconomic situation	CAMELS	databank.mefa.ir	Million Rials
GDP	GDP	databank.mefa.ir	Billion Rials
Bank Investments	Investment	cbi.ir/page/4275.aspx	Billion Rials
Total deposits of individuals in the hands	Tdiwb	cbi.ir/page/4275.aspx	Billion Rials
Bank Bankruptcy Risk	bankruptcy	databank.mefa.ir/	Billion Rials

Research findings

First, the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the model are examined, which are reported in Table 2 of the statistics related to the mean, median, maximum, minimum and Jark-Barra test.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Jarque-Bera	Possibility
Tdiwb	34/173	24/310	95/690	10/660	8/580	0/0137
bankruptcy	23/437	17/260	53/095	10/939	8/656	0/0031
CAMELS	29/564	22/60	53/500	11/090	6/967	0/0003
GDP	271990	175585	778032	147120	35/567	0/0000
Investment	31/903	33/350	60/670	13/200	6/800	0/0039
TLGSU	28/163	18/900	76/600	10/100	9/369	0/0092

The results obtained from the statistical analysis of the data reported in Table (3) show that all the studied variables have a probability statistic of less than 0.05 m. Thus, the null hypothesis of the Jark-Berra test can be rejected, which means that with a probability of more than 99%, it can be said that the null hypothesis of this test that the distribution of the data of these variables is normal is rejected and we conclude All the variables mentioned in Table (4) do not follow the normal distribution in the period 2017-2022 After the results of the descriptive statistics are determined, the root test of the research variables should be examined. Therefore, one of the important issues in estimating econometric models is the nature of the data in terms of reliability, because if the statistical data are unstable, we may suffer from false regression. Therefore, the variables used in the model in terms of reliability with the help of a group of reliability tests, the results are shown in Table (4).

Table 4. Unit Root Test

variables	LLC		Im, Pesaran		ADF		Obvers
	Statistic	Prob	Statistic	Prob	Statistic	Prob	
Tdiwb	-4/8691	0/0000	-0/248	0/4019	49/186	0/2733	132
bankruptcy	-55/619	0/0000	-7/554	0/0000	58/447	0/0711	132
CAMELS	-53/693	0/0000	-8/576	0/0531	92/364	0/0078	132
GDP	-25/786	0/0000	-2/968	0/0015	64/115	0/0254	132
Investment	-19/830	0/0000	-2/880	0/0020	66/895	0/0146	132
TLGSU	-1/437	0/0753	1/289	0/0036	14/324	0/0853	132

Based on the results reported in Table (4), which shows the different tests of the single root for six time series, it shows that the variables of bankruptcy risk, macroeconomic status, GDP, and investment are based on the generalized Dickey Fuller, Hashem-Pasaran and Levin, Lin and Chu Mana tests. On the other hand, the variable of total deposits of individuals with the bank based on the test Dickie Fuller's are generalized and Levin, Lin and Chu Mana are generalized. Finally, the microcredit variable is based on the Hashem-Mana Sons test. In the following, the effects of bank bankruptcy risk on microcredit in Iran are predicted using artificial intelligence genetic algorithms. (5 and 6) will be as follows:

Table 5. Predicting Bankruptcy Risk Using C5-0

CP ²	nsplit	rel error	xerror	xstd
0/7361	0	1/0000	1/0317	0/1430
0/1526	1	0/2638	0/2904	0/0541
0/0490	2	0/1112	0/1776	0/0278
0/0248	3	0/0621	0/1154	0/0246
0/0100	4	0/0373	0/1032	0/0248
Variable importance				
Variable	importance	MSE	Rne	CP
Bankruptcy	19	3/6735	342/59	0/7631
camels	12			
investment	12			
Tdbiwh	23			
GDP	23			

The decision tree algorithm (rpart) analysis revealed the impact of different factors on microcredit in Iran. Bank bankruptcy risk had 19% significance, while GDP, macroeconomic condition index and total bank deposits each had 23% significance. Bank investment had the least impact with 12%. This suggests that while all variables play a role in predicting microcredit, bank bankruptcy risk, financial indicators, macroeconomic conditions, and total bank deposits have a more significant impact than bank investment. In particular, bank failure risk and GDP emerged as the most important determinants in predicting microcredit allocation. The high importance of these indicators in the model demonstrates their significant impact on bank lending and the microeconomy. In essence, the financial health of banks and the economic condition of the country can significantly affect the availability of financial resources to small and medium enterprises. This analysis also showed that microcredit is an important tool for promoting entrepreneurship and reducing income inequality. Financial indicators and GDP reflect the overall economic situation of the country, which affects economic opportunities and, consequently, income inequality. The performance of the model was evaluated using the xstd and xerror indices, which show the average standard deviation and standard error, respectively. The CP value decreased from 0.736 to 0.0100, indicating a balance between model complexity and its ability to generalize to new data. This study showed that combining the decision tree approach with neural networks provides a deeper and more accurate method for data analysis because neural networks identify more complex patterns in the data and perform better in predicting non-linear economic processes. This combined approach is useful for banks and economic decision makers in Iran to better plan to promote growth and reduce economic disparities. Therefore, Table 6 discusses the prediction of bankruptcy risk using the reinforcement gradient.

² complexity param

Table 5. Results of the Reinforcement Gradient Reinforcement Learning Model

Feature	Gain	Cover	Frequency
GDP	0/013786	0/23149	0/23764
camels	0/596101	0/20140	0/18403
Bankruptcy	0/073155	0/15823	0/17391
investment	0/279217	0/19933	0/13698
Tdbiwh	0/037739	0/20953	0/26742
Class: character/ Mode: character			
	Gain	Cover	Frequency
Min.	0/13698	0/15823	0/013786
1st Qu.	0/17391	0/19933	0/037739
Median	0/18403	0/20140	0/073155
Mean	0/020000	0/020000	0/020000
3rd Qu.	0/23764	0/20953	0/279217
Max.	0/26742	0/23149	0/596101
MSE			0/00186
RMSE			2/5812

The statistical analysis in table 6 shows the effect of bank bankruptcy risk on microcredit in Iran. Based on the results of Table 6, it can be seen that GDP has shown the highest frequency, which shows its importance in predicting the level of microcredit, although the profit is relatively small. This has shown the indirect effect or mediating effects of GDP through other variables. CAMELS indices, which represent factors such as interest rates, exchange rates and inflation, have the highest gain, which has shown their significant impact in predicting the risk and ability of banks to grant microcredit. Bank failure risk, which consists of factors such as bank value, liquidity, bank assets and liabilities, is considered a very important variable in the model with an average gain. This has shown that failure risk has improved the prediction of microcredit on average, reflecting the importance of banks' financial conditions in determining their stability and creditworthiness. Therefore, bank investments and total bank deposits (Tdbiwh) have also been evaluated as important in terms of frequency and gain, which has shown their direct and important role in determining the volume of microcredits. These variables have been considered as indicators of incentive policies and credit facilities that have enabled banks to respond to the financial needs of small and medium borrowers. Finally, after the results of the learning algorithms (machine learning) have been determined, it is now time to conduct the final review of the research using ANN artificial intelligence, the results of which are as follows in Table (7).

This research has investigated the effect of bank bankruptcy risk on microcredit in Iranian economy using neural networks. The results showed that the GDP had the least definitive damage and had a significant impact on the prediction model. This has shown the importance of GDP in the ability of the banking system to provide microcredit. The risk of bank bankruptcy has shown the highest amount of definitive damage, which indicates the high importance of this variable in predicting microcredit. Indicator components of the macroeconomic situation, including interest rate, exchange rate and inflation, have been significantly effective in analyzing banking risk and the ability of banks as lenders. Total bank deposits and bank investments are also known as important

factors in this analysis, which indicate the current financial condition of the bank and its ability to create development and growth in the economy. Therefore, the analyses have shown that several key factors are effective in predicting microcredit in Iran. These findings are useful for improving financial and credit policies and economic planning at the national level. The risk of bank bankruptcy has been identified as an important factor in evaluating and making decisions related to lending. The results also showed that changes in macroeconomic policies, such as inflation and interest rates, affected banks' ability to lend and ultimately income inequality. The predictive models ranged from close to zero to close to one, indicating a wide range of states. The results have also shown that predictive variables such as total loans are affected by bank bankruptcy, which emphasizes the importance of the strength and financial health of banks in assessing and granting loans and distributing financial resources in society. These results have shown the need to conduct more research and apply deeper economic approaches in order to provide corrective solutions in advancing the country's financial and banking policies. Finally, Graph 1 confirms the contents of Table 7.

Table 7. Final Review of Research Models Based on Artificial Intelligence ANN

Row	Variable	Mean dropout loss	Label
1	full model	0/0713	Nnet
2	Bankruptcy	0/0024	Nnet
3	Tdbiwh	0/0465	Nnet
4	camels	0/0071	Nnet
5	investment	0/0297	Nnet
6	GDP	0/0010	Nnet
RMSE for Tlgsu Model			0/0112
predicted values		Min	Max
predicted values		-1/47	3/08
residuals		-1/03	0/06

Figure (1). Fact-checking or mere prediction of AI ANNs

Figure (1) The reporter compares the accuracy of the predictions of the neural network model (Tlgsu: Actual vs Predicted) with the actual data. In this graph, the horizontal axis (X-axis) displays the real values and the vertical axis (Y-axis) It shows the values predicted by the model. The points seen in the image each represent a data or a sample in the dataset that was tested. The diagonal line in the graph represents the ideal, so that if all the predictions were exactly in line with the actual data, the points would be placed exactly on this line. Looking at the distribution of points in the image, it can be seen that most of the points close to the line are one-to-one, indicating that the model's predictions are close to the actual data in many cases. The lack of points away from the line indicates that there are no large errors in the predictions, and the model generally provides good prediction performance. Also, the distribution of points around the diagonal line indicates that the variance of the prediction error shows that there are fewer errors in the predicted and actual values. This graph can help analysts ensure the degree of alignment between the predicted and actual data and confirm the reliability of the model. Overall, the graph shows that the neural network model has been able to predict microcredit with acceptable accuracy and is a useful tool for investigating bank bankruptcy risk and its impact on microcredit. This predictive accuracy can be useful in economic planning and policy decision-making. In conclusion, the research uses the SVM learning algorithm to evaluate the accuracy and accuracy of the research models to ensure the results of the research, the results of which are also described in Tables (8).

Table 8. Investigating Research Models Based on SVM Learning Algorithm

Overall statistics		Class1	Class2	Class3
Accuracy	0/9425	0/8973	1/0000	0/9874
95% CI	(0/4032, 0/9616)	0/9182	0/8837	0/8921
No Information Rate	0/002	0/7632	0/9452	0/9648
P-value [Acc> NIR]	0/0000	1/0000	0/9021	1/0000
Kappa	0/9551	0/9638	0/8231	0/9320
McNemar's Test P-Value	0/001	0/9008	1/0000	0/8901

Based on the information in Table 8, Support Vector Machine (SVM) was used to examine the effect of bankruptcy risk on microcredit. In this model, factors such as GDP, economic mirror index (including inflation, exchange rate and interest rate), total bank deposits, investment and bank bankruptcy were considered as explanatory variables. The reported results show an accuracy of 0.94 percent, which is considered acceptable. The p-value obtained for the model is very low, indicating that the probability that the observed accuracy is due to chance is close to zero. The kappa coefficient for the model is 0.95, indicating high accuracy and adequacy of the models in prediction. The very low P values of the test also indicate a low probability of a difference between the accuracy of positive and negative predictions of the models. The modeling results have confirmed that bank bankruptcy has a significant impact on microcredit in the Iranian economy. The values obtained for sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value in all three classes are close to 1, demonstrating the ability of the model to accurately separate and classify samples. Prevalence and detection rate also have values very close to 1, indicating an equal distribution of classes in the analyzed data. Overall, the results emphasize that bank bankruptcy affects microcredit. These results have shown the importance of considering the efficiency of macroeconomic policies and the risk-

taking of banks and financial institutions in relation to the overall economic situation and the financial capability of individuals and households. In conclusion, the results emphasize that bank bankruptcy affects microcredit. Finally, the efficiency of macroeconomic policies and the risk-taking of banks and financial institutions on the macroeconomic situation and the financial capability of individuals and households should be taken into account.

The results of this study show that the risk of bank failure has a significant impact on the provision of microcredit in the Iranian economy. This issue is important from several perspectives. First, the health and financial stability of banks, as the main financial intermediaries, play a key role in the optimal allocation of resources in the economy. When banks face a high risk of bankruptcy, their ability to provide credit, especially to low-income groups and small businesses, is reduced. This can lead to a widening of income gaps and economic inequality. Therefore, maintaining the health of the banking system is necessary for stability and overall economic growth. On the other hand, the results of this research show the importance of macroeconomic indicators such as GDP and inflation in predicting the risk of bank failure. This finding suggests that bank performance is strongly influenced by macroeconomic conditions. Indeed, instability and economic fluctuations can threaten the health of banks by reducing the income of households and firms and increasing defaults. Therefore, the adoption of appropriate monetary and fiscal policies to control inflation and achieve sustainable economic growth is crucial to reduce the risk of bank failure and expand microfinance.

The high accuracy of the models used in this research also demonstrates the ability of new data analysis methods, such as machine learning and neural networks, to predict economic and financial variables. By overcoming the limitations of traditional econometric models, these methods offer the possibility of extracting hidden patterns from large volumes of data and making more accurate predictions of future developments. The application of these approaches, together with the theoretical knowledge of economics, can contribute to a deeper understanding of economic dynamics and to the adoption of evidence-based policies. In conclusion, this research, using modern methods of data analysis, provides significant empirical evidence on the importance of bank failure risk in the provision of microcredit in the Iranian economy. The findings, while consistent with the theoretical literature, highlight the need for institutional reforms in the banking system to promote financial stability and expand access to finance, especially for low-income groups and small businesses. The findings also highlight the importance of coordinating macroeconomic and prudential policies to reduce systemic banking risk and achieve inclusive growth.

Conclusion and Research Suggestions

The main objective of this research is to predict the impact of bankruptcy risk on microcredit in 28 Iranian banks for the period 2017-2022, using machine learning and neural networks.

In this study, neural network models (ANNs) were evaluated to predict the amount of microcredit and the effects of various financial and economic variables on them. These models were used with variables including GDP, macroeconomic condition index (interest rate, exchange rate, inflation), total bank deposits, and investment factors. The

results of the study show that bank bankruptcy risk has a significant effect on microcredit in Iran's economy. The dropout loss values of this model for the GDP variable were very low, indicating the great importance of the macroeconomy in the ability of the banking system to provide microcredit. Bank bankruptcy risk has been identified as the variable with the highest dropout loss in the model, indicating the significant impact of this risk on lending decisions. This shows that the financial condition of banks and their health play an important role in granting loans and distributing financial resources in society. The economic mirror index has also been used as one of the key components in predicting bank bankruptcy risk, and with relatively low loss values, it has shown its effectiveness in analyzing the situation of banks. Total bank deposits and investment factors have also been identified as two other components that can be important indicators for measuring the capacity and financial sustainability of banks and economic growth development. In this research, in addition to neural networks, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) machine learning algorithm has also been used to validate the results. The results of the model evaluation by SVM had high accuracy and showed the model's ability to predict microcredit. The P-Value obtained for the model indicates that the probability of this accuracy being accidental is low, and the kappa coefficient shows good agreement between the actual data and the model's predictions. Also, sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive value in this analysis is close to one for all three classes, which indicates the very high accuracy and precision of the model in classification and prediction.

In conclusion, this study finds that the use of advanced artificial intelligence tools such as neural networks and SVM can accurately help in predicting and assessing bank failure risk and its impact on microcredit in Iran. This information can be used by policy makers and financial institutions to improve their decision making and develop more effective strategies against financial risks, thereby facilitating access to financial resources and reducing economic inequalities. The results of this study are consistent with the findings of several other studies, including the research of Ahmadian (2014) and Zarei and Kamijani (2015) on the predictors of banking crisis, Ebrahimi Salari et al. (2018) and Dehghani and Jamini (2018) in the field of microfinance, Contreras et al. (2023) and Mahaputri and Satrianto (2024) on risk management of banks and supporting micro sectors of the economy in reducing income inequality and economic development. These findings confirm the role and importance of the various financial and economic development. These findings confirm the role and importance of various financial and economic variables and how they affect microcredit in Iran.

This study shows that managing bank failure risk and improving macroeconomic conditions are effective in strengthening the microcredit sector and reducing income inequality. Banks and regulatory bodies should focus particularly on improving asset quality and precise management of bank balance sheets. This can include improving risk assessment and analysis systems, strengthening capital bases, and increasing transparency in bank financial reporting.

Also, given the importance of microcredit in job creation for the weaker sections of society and the equal distribution of economic opportunities, more guarantees should be created for a sustainable flow of resources in this regard. Policymakers should focus on structural reforms and support for productive sectors with the aim of increasing

production levels and improving economic growth in terms of macroeconomic indicators such as GDP. This increase in production can lead to strengthening the demand for microcredit and improve the overall health of the country's financial system.

Recommendations

Banks and regulatory bodies should focus on improving asset quality and precise management of bank balance sheets. This can include improving risk assessment and analysis systems, strengthening capital bases, and increasing transparency in financial reporting.

More guarantees should be created for a sustainable flow of resources towards microcredit. Limitation of these credits can cause problems for a wide range of agricultural, production, and service activities and weaken job stability.

Policymakers should focus on structural reforms and support for productive sectors with the aim of increasing production levels and improving economic growth. This can lead to strengthening the demand for microcredit and improve the overall health of the financial system.

Stability of macroeconomic variables such as inflation rate, exchange rate, and real interest rate should be one of the national policy priorities so that banks can lend with greater confidence.

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